

Transition Pathways for Botswana: Comparative Scenario Analysis under National Development and Climate Commitments

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Executive Summary

This study evaluates alternative power-sector transition pathways for Botswana using the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) and assesses how national electricity planning can align with climate commitments while maintaining a least-cost system development. Botswana's electricity supply is currently heavily coal-dependent, creating a policy misalignment between the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) and the country's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 15% by 2030.

Three scenarios were analysed for 2022–2050: an NDC 15% emissions-reduction scenario, and a more ambitious scenario targeting 50% renewable electricity by 2036. The baseline pathway locks the system into coal reliance and high emissions. In contrast, emissions-constrained scenarios shift the generation mix toward solar and wind, demonstrating that Botswana can meet its NDC target within a least-cost framework through accelerated deployment of renewables.

Achieving climate targets increases annualised investment costs by roughly 22–26% but requires more than doubling installed capacity, largely driven by utility-scale solar expansion. Importantly, the modest cost increase indicates that Botswana's current NDC target is economically non-binding and insufficient to drive deep structural change.

Increased emissions targets, the rollout of renewables, and investment in storage and grid flexibility are essential to avoid long-term coal lock-in and to align power-sector planning with Botswana's renewable resource potential.

1. Introduction

Botswana's power sector stands at a critical juncture, shaped by competing imperatives of economic development, energy security, and climate mitigation (Tamasiga et al., 2025). Electricity generation remains coal-dominated, accounting for approximately 98% of domestic output and about 87% of greenhouse gas emissions (Saad et al., 2024).

Botswana has committed under its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to reduce national greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 15% by 2030 (Government of Botswana,

2016). This NDC emissions target appears misaligned with the coal-centric expansion outlined in the 2020 Integrated Resource Plan (IRP).

This policy misalignment raises important questions regarding the cost, feasibility, and structural implications of alternative power-sector pathways. While the IRP prioritises least-cost supply adequacy in the medium term, it risks locking in emissions that undermine Botswana's climate commitments. Conversely, Botswana possesses among the highest solar resources globally, which remain underutilised (Tlhalerwa & Mulalu, 2019).

Given the above background, this study applies a scenario-based energy modelling approach to examine how Botswana's power sector evolves under different policy constraints. Specifically, the study addresses two research questions:

(1) What are the power-sector implications of Botswana's IRP if implemented as planned?

(2) What is the minimum-cost power-system pathway that achieves Botswana's NDC targets of 15% emissions reductions and 50% Renewables (Solar Target) in 2036. .

2. Methodology

Modelling approach and tool

The analysis employs the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), a bottom-up, linear cost-optimisation framework widely used for long-term energy planning (Howells et al., 2011). OSeMOSYS is demand-led, minimises total discounted system costs comprising capital, fixed, variable, and emissions-related costs while meeting electricity demand and policy constraints. The model was implemented using a national, single-region representation of Botswana's power sector over the period 2022–2050. The years 2024-2050 were taken as the calibration period.

Data sources

Core techno-economic inputs were drawn from various sources, including AFREC, IRENA, and IEA data sets, supplemented with country-specific updates from Botswana's IRP and utility reports. Demand projections follow the IRP business-as-usual trajectory, assuming average annual growth of approximately 3%. Technology costs, efficiencies, capacity factors, fuel prices, and emissions factors are based on internationally harmonised datasets and peer-reviewed literature

Key assumptions

The model assumes perfect foresight, least-cost behaviour, and no institutional constraints on investment. Renewable energy potentials are exogenously constrained based on resource assessments, while coal and import capacities reflect existing

infrastructure and IRP commitments. Emissions are accounted for using fuel-specific CO₂ emission facto

Scenarios

Three scenarios are analysed: (i) a Baseline (IRP-consistent) pathway reflecting current policy implementation; (ii) a 15% emissions-reduction scenario aligned with Botswana’s NDC; and (iii) 50% renewables (Solar Target) by 2036.

3. Results

Electricity Generation

The baseline pathway locks the power system into continued dependence on coal across the entire modelling horizon, with electricity imports increasing steadily to meet rising demand. Renewable energy deployment remains marginal, with solar PV contributing 0.5 % (11.9 PJ) of annual generation by 2050 (see figure 1). This trajectory entrenches a carbon-intensive electricity mix and exposes the system to long-term economic, environmental, and energy-security risks.

By contrast, emissions-constrained pathways fundamentally reorient the system away from coal toward domestic renewable energy, led by solar PV. Under the 15% emissions-reduction (NDC-aligned) scenario, solar generation expands more than fourfold relative to the baseline, reaching 7.5% (53.0 PJ) by 2050, complemented by modest onshore wind deployment. The Solar Target Scenario goes further, raising solar output to about 57.5 PJ, this is an increase of roughly 4 PJ beyond the NDC pathway—demonstrating that stronger renewable commitments deliver materially deeper decarbonisation.

Figure 1: Full Electricity Generation across the three scenarios

Annualised Investment Costs

Achieving the NDC target results in only an increase in annualised investment costs of approximately 26% relative to the baseline, accompanied by substantial expansion in installed capacity (see figure 2). Accumulated installed capacity in the Solar Target Scenario Increases by 22%, driven primarily by utility-scale solar PV, highlighting the central role of solar in Botswana’s least-cost decarbonisation strategy

Figure 2: Annualised investment costs across the three scenarios

Emissions

Insights and implications

The results demonstrate that Botswana can achieve its current NDC target at relatively low incremental system cost, largely by exploiting its exceptional solar resource endowment. However, the limited cost differential between the baseline and the 15% emissions-reduction scenario reveals a deeper structural issue: the NDC target is insufficiently ambitious to meaningfully alter long-term investment patterns. Coal capacity remains economically attractive in the absence of stronger constraints, leading to substantial emissions lock-in under IRP-aligned planning.

From a policy perspective, this finding is critical. It suggests that incremental emissions targets risk creating a false sense of progress while delaying the deeper transition required for long-term climate alignment. Stronger, binding emissions caps or explicit coal phase-out policies would be necessary to redirect investment decisively toward low-carbon technologies.

Technologies and policy priorities

Solar PV emerges as the dominant least-cost mitigation option across all constrained scenarios, supported by declining technology costs and high-capacity factors. Complementary investments in battery storage and grid flexibility will be essential to manage variability as solar penetration increases. Wind power plays a secondary but valuable role, particularly in diversifying the renewable portfolio.

Policy priorities should therefore include:

- (i) Updating the IRP to explicitly integrate emissions constraints and long-term decarbonisation goals. Relative to the BAU pathway (368 Mton), emissions decline by 27.4% under the 15% NDC scenario and by 35.3% under the Solar Target scenario
- (ii) Strengthening renewable procurement frameworks to accelerate utility-scale solar deployment. Policy-constrained scenarios show a system-wide shift to solar-led generation, increasing solar output from ~11.9 PJ (BAU) to ~53–59 PJ by 2050 in the 15% NDC Scenario and Solar Target Scenario respectively.
- (iii) Enhancing regulatory certainty to crowd in private investment, particularly for storage and grid infrastructure;
- (iv) Gradually reducing reliance on coal imports and domestic coal generation through clearly signalled phase-down pathways.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, OSeMOSYS assumes perfect foresight and least-cost optimisation, abstracting from political economy and institutional barriers that may slow real-world deployment. Second, the analysis focuses exclusively on the power sector and does not capture economy-wide interactions or demand-side mitigation options.

7. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Botswana's current IRP-aligned power-sector pathway remains heavily coal-dependent and locks in nearly five times higher cumulative emissions than alternative low-carbon trajectories. While this pathway satisfies short-term least-cost objectives, it is fundamentally misaligned with Botswana's long-term climate and energy security goals. Results from the OSeMOSYS modelling show that Botswana can meet its existing NDC target of at least a 15% emissions reduction by 2030 through accelerated deployment of solar PV and, to a lesser extent, wind power, without imposing significant economic burdens on the system.

Importantly, the Net Zero aligned pathway achieves substantial emissions reductions with only an increase of around 22% in annualised investment costs, despite requiring a doubling of installed capacity. More ambitious NDC targets would better avoid long-term emissions lock-in, reduce import dependence, and align power-sector planning with Botswana's comparative advantage in renewable energy. Future research should therefore explore higher ambition scenarios—such as 30–40% emissions reductions by 2030—to define a more appropriate and feasible ambition range.

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